

PREPARATION IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE OF STAKEHOLDERS AND STUDENTS FOR TRAINING IN A SPECIALISED LABORATORY DURING MOBILITY

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ABSTRACT. The mobility of students and teachers is a priority of the European Union and, as its member; Bulgaria participates in the provided and financed programmes. In this regard, the article presents a brief and algorithmic approach to preparing instructions in English for safety in an electrical laboratory. Initially, several standard instructions are offered, and then explanations of the possible harms are given. Examples of the applicability of the algorithm are also given at the stage of foreign language training of students according to their level of language proficiency. The materials are adapted for different levels of foreign language knowledge.

Key words: mobility, specialised laboratory, electrical equipment, instructions, foreign language training.

ПОДГОТОВКА НА ЧУЖД ЕЗИК НА ЗАИНТЕРЕСОВАНИ СТРАНИ И СТУДЕНТИ ЗА ОБУЧЕНИЕ В СПЕЦИАЛИЗИРАНА ЛАБОРАТОРИЯ ПРИ ОСЪЩЕСТВЯВАНЕ НА МОБИЛНОСТ

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РЕЗЮМЕ. Мобилността на студентите и преподавателите е приоритет на Европейския съюз и България като негов член участва в предоставените и финансираните програми. Във връзка с това в статията е представен кратък и алгоритмичен подход за изготвяне на инструкции на английски език за безопасност в електротехническа лаборатория. Първоначално се предлагат няколко стандартни инструкции, а след това и обяснения за възможните вреди. Дават се примери за приложимост на алгоритъма и на етап чуждоезиково обучение на студенти според нивото на владеене на езика. Материалите са адаптирани за различните нива на знание на чуждия език.

Ключови думи: мобилност, специализирана лаборатория, електротехника, инструкции, чуждоезиково обучение.

Introduction

According to statistics, 3,200 projects from 84,000 organisations with over 1.3 million participants and a funding of 4.5 billion dollars take part in the *Erasmus+* programme (“Factsheets and statistics on Erasmus+ - Erasmus+,” 2025). Of these funds, €19,110,619 was used for higher education in Bulgaria alone in 2023. This is the most famous programme in the field of higher and secondary schools, which is also the best funded.

Local inter-university projects exist which provide additional opportunities for lecturers and students to visit foreign educational and scientific institutions for training, exchange of experience, and teaching (“Four ways universities can enhance their community impact,” 2024). These may be partners with the local community, such as for acquiring knowledge on the part of stakeholders in business organisations. Another well-known option is for a particular institute to conduct research, innovation, or training on a topic assigned by the business in order to fill in the gaps in the community. Many programmes for developing and implementing innovations to enhance sustainable development have been gaining popularity in recent years, including the production, distribution, and consumption of energy while maintaining its quality. The latter proves that mobility is not an end in itself, but an organised process. Its importance and participants are growing annually.

In connection with the available opportunities, each university must be ready to welcome foreign students and interested business people and help them quickly adapt to the educational and scientific process. Preparation for work in an electrical, mechanical, chemical, or other engineering laboratory is very specific. In this article, we particularly focus on the preparation of instructions for work in an electrical engineering

laboratory. For this purpose, first an algorithm for presenting the material has been prepared; then, the most important regulations are cited; basic instructions are given; and finally, several examples are offered of possible damage in case of incorrect operation of the equipment. The described algorithm is also applicable in the training of Bulgarian students leaving for / participating in an international mobility. They are also obliged to observe the established safety rules at the university they are visiting. Therefore, they must also know the foreign language to an extent allowing them to understand the rules. This, in turn, determines the timely, high-quality, and thematically focused foreign language training of the students. To increase the level of comprehensibility, examples are given according to the level of proficiency in a foreign language.

Risks when working in an electrical engineering laboratory

The preparation of safety instructions, their translation, and presentation to students are performed according to a predefined order. The algorithm is as follows:

- The main hazards in a laboratory are defined; in this case considering an electrical engineering type, for electrical materials, or an electronics laboratory;
- The regulatory framework is reviewed;
- Basic safety rules are prepared;
- The method of delivering the briefing is determined;
- Some remarks are formulated, focusing on specific features and scientific research;
- The rules are translated for three levels of proficiency in English.

Fig.1. Students in a laboratory with a short circuit hazard

Hazards in laboratories are classified into:

- those with the occurrence of a short circuit,
- those with the occurrence of a fire,
- avoiding damage to equipment or a device.

To protect against the above, planning activities are carried out to reduce the risk (Asparuhov, 2014). In the manufacturing of high-tech equipment, stricter requirements are imposed regarding the presence of flammable materials or reagents (Asparuhov, 2015).

After the planning, the instructions are prepared. The hazards in laboratories are various, but the basic instructions are based on the regulations and the law. The most important of those are:

- Ordinance № 3 (“Ordinance No. 3 of June 9, 2004 on the design of electrical and power transmission lines,” 2018);
- Health and safety regulations when working in electrical installations of electric heating plants and on electrical grids (“Regulations for safety and health when working in electrical installations of electric heating plants and on electrical networks,” 2004) (State Gazette, issue 34/2004);
- Health and safety regulations when working with electrical equipment with voltage of up to 1000V (State Gazette, issue 21/2005);
- In the presence of machines, Ordinance № 02-01 (“Regulation No. RD-02-20-1 of June 12, 2018 on technical rules and regulations for control and acceptance of electrical installation work,” 2018) is used as well;
- The technical rules and standards for the control and approval of electrical installation works (“Regulations on the design and safe operation of transmission and distribution gas pipelines, and of natural gas facilities, installations, and appliances”, n.d.);
- Regulations on the design and safe operation of transmission and distribution gas pipelines, and of natural gas facilities, installations, and appliances”, 2018 /NUBEPGRSIUPG/ - adopted by Decree of the

Council of Ministers № 171 of 16th July 2004, amended by State Gazette, issue 60 of 20th July 2018.

Laboratory rules are mandatory. Usually, the legal foundations, the basic rules and responsibilities, along with the official in charge, are stated.

Briefings

Visitors to the laboratories are made familiar with the rules through briefings. Depending on the hazard, briefings may be given at each entry, once a semester, or at a certain frequency: on a monthly basis, every other month, etc. Usually, the responsible officials are also briefed and have a certain classification group.

Special cases

Sometimes, briefings need to include provisions based on special cases or specific studies. These include the construction of buildings and laboratories close to a high-voltage network; supply with non-conventional energy sources; or additional installations for storing substances. They all must comply with the good practices not just in the operation, but also in the construction and the granting of permits for admissibility for use. Cases like these, supported by relevant studies, may include the following:

- Parameters of current when a person is in contact with conductive objects under high-voltage power lines (Petrov et al., 2023);
- Assessment of possible injuries when current from the electrical circuit passes through the human body (Petrov et al., 2022);
- Special fire prevention practices during construction, work in and operation of buildings (Vladkova, 2020);
- Parameters of gas and hydrogen pressure, their barometric characteristics, and the pressure exerted on the pipes which transport them (Vlaykova et al., 2024).

Fig.2. Short circuit on the human body

It can be seen that according to the specialty and the capabilities of the laboratory, there are various good practices. The job of specialists and laboratory managers is to monitor publications and research and select the most appropriate ones for a particular laboratory. Official rules should not be ignored. They need to be included in the major briefing. However, it is always appropriate to include examples of possible negative consequences according to the studies of specialists.

The introduction of the instructions to the persons must be followed by their understanding and compliance. That is why it is necessary to give examples of the possible accidents in case instructions are overlooked.

Training procedures

There are several options for preparing students for work in a specialised laboratory:

- One is direct briefing upon arrival at the site;
- The other is through distance learning, even before students arrive at the host institution. This can be performed in several ways:
 - through materials prepared in advance and sent out, with which students or stakeholders become familiar;
 - conducted in a remote environment via an online platform – asynchronously or synchronously (Department of Electronics, University of Ruse Angel Kanchev, Ruse, Bulgaria et al., 2022);
 - remote work in a virtual laboratory (Hristova et al., 2021).

The trainee feedback depends on the method of implementation. The goal is that after the briefing or reading the written instructions, they will have understood the basic safety rules and their obligation not to violate those.

The relationship between regulations and English language learning

English textbooks and manuals teach regulations and offer exercises to master them as speech patterns / oral statements. They are compatible with the rules in laboratories, regardless of their type. Here, we share our experience in foreign language safety training for students in electrical engineering specialties and for those studying oil and gas drilling and extraction. Through planned exercises, students themselves can consolidate knowledge not only in a foreign language, but also remember the necessary rules for visiting a laboratory or when doing field work.

In the elementary level of English language learning (A1) or from A1 to A2, safety rules when working with electricity are introduced with the study of modal verbs (Abbs and Freebairn, 1992):

- *must* and *have to* - to express [+degrees of duty or obligation];
- *must not* and *do not have to/does not have to* - to express [+degrees of prohibition].

Examples:

You must switch off the apparatus/tools/computers after work.

You must wear PPE on the oil rig.

You must turn off your mobile phone.

You have to look after your equipment.

You must not touch live wires with bare hands.

In the intermediate level of English language training (B1 to B2), the safety rules include the study of other modal verbs and the passive voice is introduced:

- *should /should not* and *ought to / oughtn't to* - to express [+recommendation] / [+advice].

Examples:

If you are not sure, you ought to ask the supervisor / responsible officer.

First, bare wires should be checked for electricity.

Protective clothing / Protective footwear / Safety helmets must be worn in this area.

Your seatbelt has to be fastened throughout the whole flight over water.

In the subsequent level of English language learning (B2), the study of modal verbs with a perfect infinitive to express the category of [+Aspect] is added to the safety rules.

For example, for an electrical engineering laboratory, the knowledge of a modal verb plus a perfect infinitive is used to express the semantic element of [+criticism on past actions], as in:

The student ought to have plugged each apparatus in a different socket to avoid overloading the network [meaning: but they did not do so].

The student ought to have monitored the quality of insulation because the damaged insulation caused a shortcut.

The student ought to have installed only certificated devices in the network and the apparatus.

The student should not have smoked a cigarette outside the smokers' cubicle because they caused a fire [meaning: they did it, breaking the rules, and caused damage to the equipment and hazards for the personnel].

A training example for students in the course of study in *Drilling* (Frendo and Bonamy, 2012, 2011):

The roustabout should have used taglines to control the load [meaning: but they did not and the load swung to the left and right and posed a serious danger].

Conclusion

The article examines the latest trends in the mobility of participants and other stakeholders. There is an increasing interest among both Bulgarian and foreign students to visit educational institutions in partner countries or in third countries. Due to the need to brief them for safe work in electrical equipment, mechanical, machine-repair, chemical, drilling, and other laboratories, the briefing materials need to be prepared in a foreign language. Training materials which are in accordance with the regulatory framework have been prepared and are offered. The materials are adapted for different levels of foreign language knowledge. We believe that the latter is a prerequisite for quality preparation and training of students not only at the University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", but also in other universities.

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